

Lorentz Force in Special Relativity theory

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Abstract: In the special relativity theory, we know how Lorentz 4-force is invariant in special relativity theory.

Keywords: Special relativity theory, Lorentz force, Electro-magnetic field transformation

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1. INTRODUCTION

Our article's aim is that we tell how Lorentz 4-force is invariant by electro-magnetic field transformations in special relativity theory.

At first, the coordinate transformation is in Special relativity theory,

$$ct = \gamma(ct' + \frac{v}{c} x'), x = \gamma(x' + \frac{v}{c} ct'), y = y', z = z' \quad (1)$$

Therefore, Minkowski 4-force is in Special Relativity theory[5]

$$f^0 = m_0 c \frac{d^2 t}{d\tau^2} = m_0 \gamma (c \frac{d^2 t'}{d\tau^2} + \frac{v}{c} \frac{d^2 x'}{d\tau^2}) = \gamma (f'^0 + \frac{v}{c} f'^1), \quad (2)$$

$$f^1 = m_0 \frac{d^2 x}{d\tau^2} = m_0 \gamma (\frac{d^2 x'}{d\tau^2} + \frac{v}{c} c \frac{d^2 t'}{d\tau^2}) = \gamma (f'^1 + \frac{v}{c} f'^0) \quad (3)$$

$$f^0 = m_0 c \frac{d^2 t'}{d\tau^2}, f^1 = m_0 \frac{d^2 x'}{d\tau^2} \quad (4)$$

$$f^2 = m_0 \frac{d^2 y}{d\tau^2} = m_0 \frac{d^2 y'}{d\tau^2} = f'^2, f^3 = m_0 \frac{d^2 z}{d\tau^2} = m_0 \frac{d^2 z'}{d\tau^2} = f'^3 \quad (5)$$

Hence, in inertial frame, Lorentz 4-force is

$$F^0 = m_0 \frac{d}{dt} (\frac{cdt}{d\tau}) = q \frac{\vec{u}}{c} \cdot \vec{E} \quad (6)$$

$$\vec{F} = m_0 \frac{d}{dt} (\frac{d\vec{x}}{d\tau}) = q [\vec{E} + \frac{\vec{u}}{c} \times \vec{B}], \quad \vec{u} = \frac{d\vec{x}}{dt} \quad (7)$$

$$F'^0 = m_0 \frac{d}{dt'} (\frac{cdt'}{d\tau}) = q \frac{\vec{u}'}{c} \cdot \vec{E}' \quad (8)$$

$$\vec{F}' = m_0 \frac{d}{dt'} (\frac{d\vec{x}'}{d\tau}) = q [\vec{E}' + \frac{\vec{u}'}{c} \times \vec{B}'], \quad \vec{u}' = \frac{d\vec{x}'}{dt'} \quad (9)$$

2. INVARIANT LORENTZ 4-FORCE IN INERTIAL FRAME

In this time, Minkowski 4-force is in inertial frame.

$$\begin{aligned}
 f^0 &= m_0 c \frac{d^2 t}{d\tau^2} = q \frac{\vec{u}}{c} \cdot \vec{E} \frac{dt}{d\tau}, \quad \vec{u} = \frac{d\vec{x}}{dt}, \quad \vec{u}' = \frac{d\vec{x}'}{dt'} \\
 &= m_0 \gamma \left(c \frac{d^2 t'}{d\tau^2} + \frac{v}{c} \frac{d^2 x'}{d\tau^2} \right) = \gamma \left(f^0 + \frac{v}{c} f^1 \right) \\
 &= \gamma q \frac{\vec{u}'}{c} \cdot \vec{E}' \frac{dt'}{d\tau} + \gamma \frac{v}{c} \left[q E_x' + q \frac{1}{c} (u_y' B_z' - u_z' B_y') \right] \frac{dt'}{d\tau}
 \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 f^1 &= m_0 \frac{d^2 x}{d\tau^2} = m_0 \gamma \left(\frac{d^2 x'}{d\tau^2} + \frac{v}{c} \frac{cd^2 t'}{d\tau^2} \right) = \gamma \left(f^1 + \frac{v}{c} f^0 \right) \\
 &= \gamma \left[q E_x' + q \frac{1}{c} (u_y' B_z' - u_z' B_y') \right] \frac{dt'}{d\tau} + \gamma \frac{v}{c} \left(q \frac{\vec{u}'}{c} \cdot \vec{E}' \right) \frac{dt'}{d\tau}
 \end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

$$f^0 = m_0 c \frac{d^2 t'}{d\tau^2} = q \frac{\vec{u}'}{c} \cdot \vec{E}' \frac{dt'}{d\tau}, \quad f^1 = m_0 \frac{d^2 x'}{d\tau^2} = q \left[E_x' + \frac{1}{c} (u_y' B_z' - u_z' B_y') \right] \frac{dt'}{d\tau} \tag{12}$$

In This Time, The Transformation Of Electromagnetic Field Is In Special Relativity Theory.

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_x &= E_x', \quad E_y = \gamma E_y' + \gamma \frac{v}{c} B_z', \quad E_z = \gamma E_z' - \gamma \frac{v}{c} B_y' \\
 B_x &= B_x', \quad B_y = \gamma B_y' - \gamma \frac{v}{c} E_z', \quad B_z = \gamma B_z' + \gamma \frac{v}{c} E_y'
 \end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

Hence, If We Calculate For Proving Invariant Of Lorentz 4-Force By Eq(10),Eq(11),Eq(12),Eq(13),

T-Component Is

$$\begin{aligned}
 f^0 &= m_0 c \frac{d^2 t}{d\tau^2} = q \frac{\vec{u}}{c} \cdot \vec{E} \frac{dt}{d\tau} \\
 &= q \frac{1}{c} (u_x E_x + u_y E_y + u_z E_z) \frac{dt}{d\tau} \\
 &= q \frac{1}{c} \left[\left(\frac{u_x' + v}{1 + \frac{u_x' v}{c^2}} \right) E_x' + \frac{u_y'}{\gamma \left(1 + \frac{u_x' v}{c^2} \right)} \gamma \left(E_y' + \frac{v}{c} B_z' \right) + \frac{u_z'}{\gamma \left(1 + \frac{u_x' v}{c^2} \right)} \gamma \left(E_z' - \frac{v}{c} B_y' \right) \right] \\
 &\times \gamma \frac{dt'}{d\tau} \left(1 + \frac{u_x' v}{c^2} \right) \\
 &= \gamma q \frac{1}{c} (u_x' E_x' + u_y' E_y' + u_z' E_z') \frac{dt'}{d\tau} + \gamma \frac{v}{c} \left[q E_x' + q \frac{1}{c} (u_y' B_z' - u_z' B_y') \right] \frac{dt'}{d\tau} \\
 &= \gamma \left(f^0 + \frac{v}{c} f^1 \right)
 \end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

X-component is

$$\begin{aligned}
 f^1 &= m_0 \frac{d^2 x}{d\tau^2} = \left[q E_x + q \frac{1}{c} (u_y B_z - u_z B_y) \right] \frac{dt}{d\tau} \\
 &= \left[q E_x' + q \left(\frac{1}{c} \left(\frac{u_y'}{\gamma \left(1 + \frac{u_x' v}{c^2} \right)} \right) \gamma \left(B_z' + \frac{v}{c} E_y' \right) - \frac{u_z'}{\gamma \left(1 + \frac{u_x' v}{c^2} \right)} \gamma \left(B_y' - \frac{v}{c} E_z' \right) \right) \right] \\
 &\times \gamma \frac{dt'}{d\tau} \left(1 + \frac{u_x' v}{c^2} \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \gamma [qE_x' + q \frac{1}{c} (u_y' B_z' - u_z' B_y')] \frac{dt'}{d\tau} + \gamma \frac{v}{c} [q \frac{1}{c} (u_x' E_x' + u_y' E_y' + u_z' E_z')] \frac{dt'}{d\tau} \\
 &= \gamma (f^1 + \frac{v}{c} f^0)
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{15}$$

Y-component is

$$\begin{aligned}
 f^2 &= m_0 \frac{d^2 y}{d\tau^2} = [qE_y + q \frac{1}{c} (u_z B_x - u_x B_z)] \frac{dt}{d\tau} \\
 &= [q\gamma (E_y' + \frac{v}{c} B_z') + q (\frac{1}{c} (\frac{u_z'}{\gamma(1+\frac{u_x'v}{c^2})} B_x' - \frac{u_x'+v}{1+\frac{u_x'v}{c^2}} \gamma (B_z' + \frac{v}{c} E_y')))] \\
 &\times \gamma \frac{dt'}{d\tau} (1 + \frac{u_x'v}{c^2}) \\
 &= [qE_y' + q \frac{1}{c} (u_z' B_x' - u_x' B_z')] \frac{dt'}{d\tau} = f^2
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{16}$$

Z-component is

$$\begin{aligned}
 f^3 &= m_0 \frac{d^2 z}{d\tau^2} = [qE_z + q \frac{1}{c} (u_x B_y - u_y B_x)] \frac{dt}{d\tau} \\
 &= [q\gamma (E_z' - \frac{v}{c} B_y') + q (\frac{1}{c} (\frac{u_x'+v}{1+\frac{u_x'v}{c^2}}) \gamma (B_y' - \frac{v}{c} E_z') - \frac{u_y'}{\gamma(1+\frac{u_x'v}{c^2})} B_x')] \\
 &\times \gamma \frac{dt'}{d\tau} (1 + \frac{u_x'v}{c^2}) \\
 &= [qE_z' + q \frac{1}{c} (u_x' B_y' - u_y' B_x')] \frac{dt'}{d\tau} = f^3
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{17}$$

3. CONCLUSION

We know Lorentz 4-force is invariant by the Lorentz transformation in special relativity theory .

REFERENCES

- [1] W.Rindler, Am.J.Phys.34.1174(1966)
- [2] A.Miller, Albert Einstein’s Special Theory of Relativity(Addison-Wesley Publishing Co., Inc., 1981)
- [3] W.Rindler, Special Relativity(2nd ed., Oliver and Boyd, Edinburg,1966)
- [4] A. Einstein, “ Zur Elektrodynamik bewegter K`orper”, Annalen der Physik. 17:891(1905)
- [5] D.J. Griffiths,” Introduction To Electrodynamics”,(2nd ed.,Prentice Hall,Inc.1981)

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